

EFFICIENT NONLINEAR MULTISCALE SPECTRAL GFEM APPLIED TO COMPOSITE AEROSPACE STRUCTURES

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Composite materials for aerospace applications

Inner ply scale:
Microscopic

Plies stacked in different orientations

[Ongoing PhD – Jiraphant Srisuriyachot – University of Bath]

Carbon fibres

Inner structure scale: **Mesoscopic**

Laminated material

[Johnson, K. J., Butler, R., Loukaides, E. G., Scarth, C., & Rhead, A. T. (2019). Stacking sequence selection for defect-free forming of uni-directional ply laminates. *Composites Science and Technology*, 171, 34-43.]

Composite materials for aerospace applications

Structural detail scale

C-spar

Macroscopic scale

Composite fuselage
[GKN Fokker]

<https://www.gkn.com/aerospace>

Uncertainties:

Tapered region
Micro-tomography (μ CT) thickness measurement

Delamination

In-plane waviness

Voids

μ CT slice

CERTIFICATION FOR DESIGN: RESHAPING THE TESTING PYRAMID

Design a certification process adapted to composites for aerospace applications

- Multi-scale problem
 - Resolve stress distribution at the defect level
 - Structural effect
 - Nonlinear effect
- Uncertainty quantification (UQ) problem
 - Sub-component and upper levels
 - Virtual testing

Objectives:

- Method designed for UQ – Efficient defect assessment

I. MS-GFEM for HPC scale problem & Offline – Online method

II. Non-linear MS-GFEM

III. UM-bridge

<http://dune-project.org/>

MS-GFEM:

Multi-scale Spectral Generalized Finite Element Method

Full meso-scale model

Domain decomposition

Generalized Eigenvalue problem in the Overlaps (GenEO) [1]

Coarse approximation space

A-harmonic optimal subspace [2]:

Ensure that the eigenvectors are solutions of the homogeneous PDE on interior Degrees of Freedom (DoF)

[1] Spillane, N., Dolean, V., Hauret, P., Nataf, F., Pechstein, C., & Scheichl, R. (2014). Abstract robust coarse spaces for systems of PDEs via generalized eigenproblems in the overlaps. *Numerische Mathematik*, 126(4), 741-770.

[2] Ma, C., & Scheichl, R. (2021). Error estimates for fully discrete generalized FEMs with locally optimal spectral approximations. arXiv preprint arXiv:2107.09988.

Offline / Online method:

Offline

GMs-FEM
Massively parallel

Full meso-scale model

A-harmonic generalized Eigenvalue problem in the Overlaps (GenEO)

Online

Local update of the coarse space
Computational burden drastically reduced

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Composite problem

Large thin structure – Buckling

Implement of geometric nonlinearities in DUNE

Cho, H., Shin, S., & Yoh, J. J. (2017). Geometrically nonlinear quadratic solid/solid-shell element based on consistent corotational approach for structural analysis under prescribed motion. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, 112(5), 434-458.

Nguyen, V. A., Zehn, M., & Marinković, D. (2016). An efficient co-rotational FEM formulation using a projector matrix. *Facta Universitatis, Series: Mechanical Engineering*, 14(2), 227-240.

Newton Raphson MS-GFEM scheme

Load step loop: $F_{\Omega_i^* ext}^{t+\delta t} = F_{\Omega_i^* ext}^t + \Delta F_{\Omega_i^* ext}$

update $K_{\Omega_i^*}^{T t+\delta t}(u), F_{\Omega_i^* int}^{t+\delta t}$

Construct coarse space $V_H := \text{span}\{R_j^\top \Xi_j(\varphi_h^{j,k}|_{\Omega_j}) : k = 1, \dots, m_j, j = 1, \dots, N\}$

$K_H^{T t+\delta t}(u)$

While $\|F_{\Omega_i^* ext}^{t+\delta t} - F_{\Omega_i^* int}^{t+\delta t}\| < \epsilon \quad \|\Delta U_H^{t+\delta t}\| < \epsilon$

Solve: Local particular solution: $K_{\Omega_i^*}^{T t+\delta t} \Delta u_{\Omega_i^*}^{t+\delta t} = F_{\Omega_i^* ext}^{t+\delta t} - F_{\Omega_i^* int}^{t+\delta t}$

Coarse space solution: $K_H^{T t+\delta t} \Delta U_H^{t+\delta t} = R_H$

$U_H^{t+\delta t} = U_H^t + \Delta U_H^{t+\delta t}$

Project & update: $u_{\Omega_i^*}^{t+\delta t} \longrightarrow K_{\Omega_i^*}^{T t+\delta t}(u), F_{\Omega_i^* int}^{t+\delta t}$

update coarse system: $V_H, K_H^{T t+\delta t}(u)$

Improvements: Newton Raphson MS-GFEM scheme

Load step loop: $F_{\Omega_i^* ext}^{t+\delta t} = F_{\Omega_i^* ext}^t + \Delta F_{\Omega_i^* ext}$

update $K_{\Omega_i^*}^{T t+\delta t}(u), F_{\Omega_i^* int}^{t+\delta t}$

Construct coarse space $V_H := \text{span}\{R_j^\top \Xi_j(\varphi_h^{j,k}|_{\Omega_j}) : k = 1, \dots, m_j, j = 1, \dots, N\}$

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Improvements: Newton Raphson MS-GFEM scheme

Load step loop: $F_{\Omega_i^* ext}^{t+\delta t} = F_{\Omega_i^* ext}^t + \Delta F_{\Omega_i^* ext}$

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Construct coarse space $V_H := \text{span}\{R_j^T \Xi_j(\varphi_h^{j,k}|_{\Omega_j}) : k = 1, \dots, m_j, j = 1, \dots, N\}$

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Project & update: $u_{\Omega_i^*}^{t+\delta t} \rightarrow K_{\Omega_i^*}^{T, t+\delta t}(u), F_{\Omega_i^* int}^{t+\delta t}$

update coarse system: $V_H, K_H^{T, t+\delta t}(u)$

- Reducing load increment
- Improving coarse space
- More local iterations
- Allow re-computation of coarse space if needed

Improvements: Newton Raphson MS-GFEM scheme

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Construct coarse space $V_H := \text{span}\{R_j^\top \Xi_j(\varphi_h^{j,k}|_{\Omega_j}) : k = 1, \dots, m_j, j = 1, \dots, N\}$

$K_H^{T t+\delta t}(u)$

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Coarse space solution: $K_H^{T t+\delta t} \Delta U_H^{t+\delta t} = R_H$

$U_H^{t+\delta t} = U_H^t + \Delta U_H^{t+\delta t}$

Project & update: $u_{\Omega_i^*}^{t+\delta t} \longrightarrow K_{\Omega_i^*}^{T t+\delta t}(u), F_{\Omega_i^* int}^{t+\delta t}$

Ensure convergence if: $\|\Delta U_H^{t+\delta t}\|_{i+1} > \|\Delta U_H^{t+\delta t}\|_i$ do update coarse system: $V_H, K_H^{T t+\delta t}(u)$

force — global strains

Scalability!

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UM-bridge:

<https://um-bridge-benchmarks.readthedocs.io/en/docs/index.html>

UM-bridge:

Delaminated area

Wrinkles

Inputs:
Vector describing defect (size, angle, type, etc..)

UQ UM

HTTP

UM

Outputs:

- Failure criterion
- Global response

Quasi Monte Carlo:

Delamination defect

Strain energy distribution

< 1h for 1024 samples

Quasi Monte Carlo:
Start at a load increment
Delamination defect

Strain energy distribution

Conclusion:

- Parallelised and optimised nonlinear method with a great scalability

Perspectives:

- Associate Nonlinear MS-GFEM with Offline/Online method
- Singular Value Decomposition

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Thanks for your attention

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